

A Study on Google is an Artificial Encyclopedia Affecting Human Intelligence – An Empirical Study

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ABSTRACT

Google is opening this platform to the world, which gives us an equal opportunity to peek in and see how the company thinks about developing machine learning systems. Internally, Google has spent the last five years building a massive platform for artificial intelligence and now they're unleashing it on the world. Although Google would prefer you call it machine intelligence they feel that the word artificial intelligence carries too many connotations and fundamentally they're trying to create genuine intelligence-just in machine.

The internet makes things faster, but faster is not always necessarily. Better we don't want to sacrifice our critical thinking and uniqueness for the attainment of a modest amount of additional productivity our cognitive thinking is one of our greatest possessions and we should take this extra time to preserve it.

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KEYWORDS: Artificial, Intelligence, Technology, Human intelligence

INTRODUCTION

Everyday search engines like Google give us thousands of solutions and facilitate our lives do they also affect our brain? It seems so, according to a new study that claims that the internet has a direct impact on how our memory works.

We habitually turn to the internet to assist us with the informational demands of our current modernized lifestyle.

The internet essentially provides us with an outlet for research an opportunity to delve deeper into topics for further information and to essentially infinitely expand the information available to us. As the internet becomes increasingly intertwined within our lifestyle. It is negatively shaping the way we are processing and interpreting using the internet is reducing our desire to be inquisitive, think, comprehend and ultimately retain information.

Technology has created a huge impact on our lives in the present day, many studies significantly showed internet affecting our intelligence as we use it on daily basis for various reasons in many ways From receiving or passing information, to getting assistance in education and research field, from office work and banking to other need like entertainment, traveling, keeping up with the happenings around the globe and current affairs ; technology has shaped our lives in an entirely different spectrum and one of the biggest tools which has been used for playing the role is the internet.

Review Of Literature

- The research conducted by psychologists of Columbia and Harvard university's is the first kind to examine the effect of search engines on the human memory.
- According to a co-author of the study besty sparrow, search engines change our way of memorizing and remembering things.

- The results published in the science magazine suggest that the way our brain "saves" various data has changed significantly because of our confidence to find to find them online
- Artificial intelligence will allow us to further develop abstract thinking, imagination, and intuition. Artificial intelligence will push us to access the most complex parts of our minds. When routine work is automated, we can exploit our most human abilities. The future of society is based on individuals who access superior reasoning and can use complex skills to solve problems, explain chris brover , a professor at university London
- Some studies suggest that artificial intelligence will promote the development of all capabilities that add value to machines it will also increase safety and optimize work tools but it cannot replace the human mind when judgment and subjectivity are the distinguishing value, says German de la fuente, managing partner of deloitte one of the main auditors that has recently systematically introduced robotics into the creation of reports.
- The researchers claim that the internet has how become a dominant form of transactive memory. Recollections that are outside of our minds but we know where and how we can access them previously this role belonged to books. Today the internet shows even more powerful presence in our lives.

Objective:

“Through moderation of our internet usage we can augment our knowledge increase our productivity explore our interests and innovate if we are smart in the way we use the internet we could actually increase our desire to be inquisitive and think as it can serve as an avenue to open up research Possibilities and truly contribute to our society’s goal of productivity and efficiency”.

Statement of problem:

The Google effect has both positive and negative sides. These days we do not want to find the answer quickly and easily. This is known as the Google effect. Our reliance on the internet is increasing day by day. It is transforming the way of our thinking and how we remember the things. In other words it is altering our brains.

Methodology:

A descriptive study was taken up to study Google as an artificial encyclopedia affecting human intelligence-an empirical study this study required data to be collected from secondary data.

- Secondary data was obtained from publications, journal, books, newspaper, web site etc..

Analysis:

- Almost every person uses Google search’s once in a day it is known that 73,137 Google searches are done in one second these days.
- The average number of Google searches per day has grown from 9800 in 1998 to 4.7 trillion this may not be surprising. Since we’ve all come to appreciate the thrill of instant information but while its certainly convenient to have sum of knowledge at our fingerprints, studies show the “Google effect” is changing the way we think.
- In a 2011 experimental published in science magazine college students remembered less informational when

they knew they could easily access it later on the computer. With 49% of Americans now toting around Google on their smart phones, research’s concluded that the effect is the same we are relying on Google to store knowledge long term, instead of our own brains.

- Our brains is learning to disregard information found online, and this connection becomes stronger every time we experience it so the more we use Google, the less likely we are to retain what we see.

Conclusion:

The discussion concludes in one common agreement and that is the impact of internet on one’s intelligence differs from one individual to other hand in the end, it finally comes to one similar result that its use should be in moderation to avoid any negative outcome if used properly its significant for progress, gaining knowledge, seeking information and making great success, however, the excessive use and dependency can cause harm to one’s thinking and creative abilities therefore its encouraged to use it’s as a helping tool and not as a final resort .

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